

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – NOVEMBER 2013
(D16)HRGN 015 / HMDW 013 PERSPECTIVE OF NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 2Hrs.
ESSAY

Instructions:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answers booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks.
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers.
- Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks.

Question One

A 60 year old woman presents with iron deficiency anaemia. After investigation she is admitted for haemotransfusion. In the process of explaining the procedure to her, she tells you she is a Jehovah's Witness and so would not accept blood transfusion.

Will you go ahead and give the blood to the patient?

- a. Give reasons for your action -5 marks
- b. A 35 year old woman was referred to the OPD with a breast lump. Examination suggested that the swelling was malignant and malignant cells were confirmed on fine needle aspirate. The patient tells you that she does not want any treatment. What actions will you take as a nurse on duty -5 marks
- c. Nurses work with other professionals to provide total health care and so there is the need for collaboration.
 - i. Explain the independent function (role) of the nurse - 3marks
- a. State five expectations from the nurse in receiving and making telephone calls on the ward - 7marks

Question Two

- a. State the definition of Nursing by
 - i. Virginia Henderson - 2 marks
 - ii. Explain the definition stated above - 2 marks
- b. State three (3) importance of Maslow's theory of needs to nursing - 3 marks
- c. Betty Neuman views the client as an open system surrounded by concentric boundaries. Explain these boundaries as indicated in Neuman theory - 6 marks
- d. What does Dorothy Orem mean when she talks about self – care - 3 marks
- e. Explain the Furst and Wolf's principle of "man and his environment" - 4 marks

Question Three

Briefly discuss the tortuous and criminal liabilities as well as defence Otanka, a renowned Nurse of Face Hospital.

Day1: She failed to treat a patient because the patient is from the South of the country.

Day 2: She threw water at a patient.

Day 3: She met a patient in a narrow passage and without any violence or design of harm she touched the patient gently.

- Day 4:** She dressed as a ghost and stood at the mortuary to scare patients resulting in some having nervous shock.
- Day 5:** She locked up a patient who was asleep in a room deliberately to prevent the patient from leaving the room.
- Day 6:** She refused to clean a spilled medicine on the ground leading to a patient injuring himself by slipping.
- Day 7:** She as well as her employers would not offer any explanation when a child was accepted into their custody for treatment and the child disappeared.
- Day 8:** After she had a good deal to drunk with a patient she drove the patient in her car and the two had an accident through her negligence.
- Day 9:** She negligently broke the hand of a patient but the patient decided to seek herbal treatment leading to the rotting of the patient hand.
- Day 10:** She plays her radio very loud at the night at the ward disturbing patients.
- Day 11:** She told neighbours the HIV status of a patient who was HIV positive.
- Day 12:** She prematurely removed a conception from the uterus of a woman at her home.
- Day 13:** She cause harm to a child during the time of its birth.
- Day 14:** She mistakenly switched bottles administering a poisonous liquid to a patient instead of a harmless liquid leading to the death of the patient.
- Day 15:** She allowed a fifteen (15) years old boy to have carnal knowledge of her

Question Four

- a. i. When we refer to nurses' actions to be ethical, what do we mean? - 8 marks
- ii. List the three great Religions you have studied in class - 2marks
- b. Write short notes about these; each carries 2 marks
1. Killing
 2. Lying
 3. Stealing
 4. Abortion
 5. Suicide
 6. Murder
 7. Euthanasia
 8. Patient
 9. Life
 10. Cheating

NMTC – BEREKUM
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION DECEMBER - 2015
RGN 18 AND RM 13 PERSPECTIVE OF NURSING
TIME ALLOWED: 2HRS
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Question One

- a. i. Define the term hospital chaplain with key terms? - 2marks
- ii. In what two ways does one qualify to be employed as a hospital chaplain? - 2marks
- iii. Explain three roles played by the hospital chaplain - 6marks
- b. When and why does a Nurse have to call the Chaplain when a patient is in a danger of death? Describe - 6marks
- c. Mention four (4) of the seven Sacraments as taught by the Magisterium - 4marks

Question Two

- a. Mention any four (4) concepts of the Environment theory propounded by Florence Nightingale. - 4marks
- b. State five (5) objectives of Ghana Registered Nurses Association (GRNA) - 5marks
- c. Mention four (4) ethical principles. - 2mark
- d. Explain any three (3) of the ethical principles that you have mentioned. - 9marks

Question Three

Miss Kemerink, a 20 year old professional nurse is tasked to prepare a patient for an operation and as part of the preparation; she is to ensure that the patient signs the consent form before the commencement of the surgery.

- a. Define and explain informed consent in not more than 30 words - 2marks
- b. State the (6) SIX indications of informed consent - 3marks
- c. Explain SIX (6) criteria that can be used to distinguish a profession from other occupations - 6marks
- d. Define and explain nursing according to Virginia Henderson - 4marks
- e. Mention five functions of the nursing and midwifery council of Ghana - 5marks

Question Four

A nurse Rasputin conducted himself in the following manner. Briefly discuss if any of he is liable to any crime or tort and if so, justify same legally.

- a. He threw water at a patient who was lying on the hospital bed for insulting him
- b. He forced and fed a patient who was on hunger strike by typing that patient with a thread
- c. He locked up a patient on the top floor of the ward by closing the doors and leaving the other which if the patient uses same to escape will lead to causation of injury to himself.
- d. He dressed up like a ghost and stood near the mortuary building and successfully scared a colleague nurses into nervous shock
- e. He tort his wife about the HIV status of a patient under his care which said patient tested positive to HIV test
- f. He played a sound system at the ward disturbing a patient who could not sleep
- g. He administered what turned out to be an overdose of the drug killing several children
- h. He assisted a registered medical practitioner in the premature expulsion or removal of conception from uterus before the period gestation is complete at the sitting room of the registered medical practitioner.
- I. He hid the body of a child at his bedroom which said child was less than six (6) months old
- j. He discovered after penetration of the natural canal of a female of eighteen (18) years that she was not

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